

EFFECT OF HUMIDITY ON ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CARBON NANOTUBE-MODIFIED EPOXY

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Abstract

The high electrical conductivity of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) has motivated their incorporation into polymers for several purposes including electrical conductivity enhancement and sensing. Some studies have suggested that thin films of CNT/polymer composites can be used for humidity sensing. This study focuses on the influence of humidity on electrical conductivity of CNT-modified epoxy composite. The degree of sensitivity to humidity of the developed composite are compared to other sensing capabilities (strain and temperature). It was found that a change of humidity from 5% relative humidity (RH) to 95% RH can cause an 80% reduction in conductivity. This significant reduction must be considered if a CNT-based strain sensor is to be developed. A gauge factor of 3.7 was obtained for CNT-epoxy strain sensor suggesting ~4% change in conductivity as a result of 1% strain. This suggests that a modest change in humidity can completely compromise the accuracy of CNT-based strain sensors.

1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have great potential for enhancing the electrical conductivity of different polymers [1]. Such nano-modification is effective in addressing issues associated with electrostatic charging, electromagnetic interference and possibly lightning strike. Further, the electrically conductive network of CNTs can be used for health monitoring and sensing applications (e.g., measuring strain and matrix damage) [2]. Several studies have shown that CNT networks are piezo-resistive (i.e., strain change in the nanocomposite is proportional to electrical resistance change). Thus, strain sensing of a polymer or composite is conceptually possible through the incorporation of CNTs into a polymer composite structure [2-3]. Dimensional changes of the polymer barrier between CNT-CNT junctions in nanocomposites due to strain are at least partly responsible for the piezo-resistivity of CNT

composites [4], suggesting that humidity and temperature induced dimensional changes would also affect the conductivity of CNT networks. For this reason, several studies have focused on the potential application of CNT networks embedded into polymers for humidity sensing [5-7].

The underlying source of the sensitivity of CNT networks to humidity is disputed. Yoo *et al.* suggest that changes in resistivity are caused by polymer swelling below the percolation threshold and by charge transfer from water molecules to CNTs above the percolation threshold. This charge transfer, they claim, alters Fermi levels, increasing resistance across CNTs and across CNT-CNT junctions [8]. However, claims that the water molecules induce a charge transfer are challenged by density-functional calculations performed by Sung *et al.* [9]. Yu *et al.* [7] suggested that the increased resistance of CNTs by water uptake is caused by a weak bond between H and C atoms from water and CNTs respectively, which lowers conductivity. Liu *et al.* developed a model of resistance with respect to humidity for a CNT/ poly (Dimethyldiallyl-ammonium Chloride) film, identifying three different parameters influencing the nanocomposite resistance (tunneling barriers between CNTs, swelling of the matrix, and charge transfer from water to CNT) [10,11]. Zhao *et al.* suggested that water molecules alone introduce electrons to CNTs and decrease the amount of conducting holes in CNTs [12]. Finally, a compensation of p-type MWCNTs by water-donated electrons was identified as the main mechanism of conductivity change due to humidity for KOH doped MWCNT/PMMA film sensors [5].

The environmental factors can influence the overall electrical conductivity of a polymer nanocomposite for applications in which a certain level of conductivity is required. Therefore, whether a CNT network is used for sensing (strain, damage, etc.) or electrical conductivity enhancement, it is crucial to

quantify the influence of environmental factors, such as humidity, on the electrical conductivity of CNT composites. This work focuses on quantification of the effect of humidity and temperature on the electrical conductivity of a CNT-modified epoxy. The results of this study are compared to the sensitivity of the same CNT-based epoxy film to strain in order to emphasize on the importance of this study.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Single-walled CNTs (SWCNTs) were synthesized by the two-laser method developed at NRC as described elsewhere [13]. A solvent-processing technique, which consists of dispersing SWCNTs by ultrasonication, followed by addition of dissolved epoxy resin and solvent removal, was used to incorporate as-produced, unfunctionalized SWCNTs into the epoxy adhesive system. Curing of resin was done at room temperature resulting in composites with ~1 wt% loading of SWCNTs. Films of the nanocomposite and baseline epoxy resin with thicknesses of 0.1 and 1 mm were cured between the two glass plates coated with a release agent to facilitate the removal of freestanding films. Metal shims were placed between the two plates to control the film thickness (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Manufacturing of thin films using a steel shim and two glass substrates.

2.2 Test setup

In order to quantify the weight gain of the polymer and nanocomposite thin films due to humidity, small samples with lateral dimensions of approximately 4 mm were exposed to humidity using a DVS Advantage Dynamic Gravimetric Vapor Sorption Analyzer from Surface Measurement Systems. The in-plane electrical resistance of the nanocomposite films was obtained by measuring the current at a voltage of 1 V using a Keithley 2635A source-meter. For the electrical measurements, strips of 5 mm wide and 4 cm long were exposed to selected humidity levels using an Espec humidity chamber while the electrical resistance of the strips was recorded.

The effect of temperature on electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite (0.1 mm thick film) was also studied. The nanocomposite was dried for two days using a desiccant (calcium sulfate) in a glass container while the specimen was suspended from the container lid using the electrode wires (Fig. 2). The container was transferred to an oven and electrical conductivity was measured while temperature was gradually increased. A slow temperature ramp of 1°C/min was used to guarantee that the container temperature closely tracked the oven temperature. A voltage of 1 V was applied to the sample and the electrical current was recorded at 5°C temperature intervals using a Keithley 2635A source-meter.

The strain sensing capability of the developed CNT composite was also studied using a nanocomposite thin film of about 100 μm in thickness with lateral dimensions of 7×7 mm, cured on the surface of an insulating epoxy substrate ~ 1 mm thick (Fig. 3). Electrodes were applied to the nanocomposite using a conductive paint (DuPont 4929N). A micro-tensile test frame (Fullam Substage Test Frame) was used to apply strain (up to 1.2%) at a displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min while electrical conductivity was measured at a voltage of 1 V using a Keithley 2635A source-meter.

Fig. 2. Test setup for the measurement of temperature effect on electrical conductivity of nanocomposites after the specimen was dried.

Fig. 3. Setup for the measurement of piezoresistivity of nanocomposite films.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of temperature on electrical conductivity

Fig. 4 presents the measured electrical conductivity of already-dried CNT/epoxy nanocomposite as a function of temperature. It is clear that electrical conductivity does not show substantial sensitivity to temperature between room temperature and 100°C. This contrasts with the results of several papers that suggest that the electrical conductivity of CNT/epoxy composites can be sensitive to temperature [14-16]. One possibility is that the CNT content is insufficient or the developed nanocomposite is not sensitive to this range of temperature [15, 16].

Fig. 4. Current (conductivity) change of nanocomposite versus temperature (@ 1 volt).

3.2. Piezoresistivity of CNT composites for strain sensing

Several studies have demonstrated the sensitivity of CNT composite electrical conductivity to mechanical strain (piezoresistivity) [3-5]. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between strain and normalized resistance change measured in this work. Gauge factor, GF , of a strain sensor is defined as:

$$GF = \frac{\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}}{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

In this formula, ΔR , R_0 and ε are the resistance change, initial resistance and strain, respectively.

In this case, the calculated gauge factor, GF , for the nanocomposite was determined to be 3.7, which is a sensitivity similar to traditional metal foil strain gauges. The reported strain gauge is in general agreement with a GF of ~ 3 obtained previously for PMMA nanocomposite sensors containing 1.0 wt% multi-walled CNT [5]. Also from Fig. 5, it is clear that the relationship between strain and normalized current change remains linear up to strains of 0.012 (12000 $\mu\epsilon$), higher than the range of conventional strain sensors (typically functional below 3000 $\mu\epsilon$).

Fig. 5. Normalized resistance change versus strain for developed CNT/epoxy nanocomposite resulting in a strain gauge factor of 3.7.

3.1. Effect of humidity on electrical conductivity

Fig. 6 compares the percentage weight gain of both neat epoxy and nanocomposite films of 0.1 mm and 1 mm thickness when dried thin films were exposed to 95% relative humidity (RH) at 50°C. For films of 0.1 mm thick, it takes about 90 min to reach to 95% of maximum weight gain (12.8%) after which the sample weight becomes stable. For films 1 mm thick, the weight gain is considerably slower as only about 25% of maximum weight gain was achieved after 8 h exposure to humidity. This is expected as the moisture diffusion is much slower for thick samples (note that the thick specimen stabilizes to a maximum weight gain of 12% after one week of exposure to 95% RH).

Fig. 7 compares the percentage change of electrical conductivity over time for 0.1 mm and 1 mm thick nanocomposite films when the humidity increases from 10% RH to 95% RH (rate: 3% RH/min) at 50°C. It is clear that the increase in humidity causes a large reduction in conductivity (up to 80%). It is also apparent that the thinner specimen is considerably more sensitive than the thicker sample (80% reduction for the thinner film versus 20% reduction for the thicker film after 8 h humidity exposure), in agreement with Fig. 6. The electrical conductivity response of nanocomposite films to humidity depends on two factors: surface conductivity change and volume conductivity change. Surface conductivity change is a dominant factor for thinner films and has previously been taken advantage of in the development of humidity sensors [5-7]. This is also consistent with Fig. 8, showing that for similar weight gain, the conductivity drop is more significant for the thinner specimen. For the thicker specimen, on the other hand, the effect of volume resistivity change is greater and only a small drop in conductivity was recorded. This sample shows a slower, more continuous conductivity drop over time (Fig. 7) and versus moisture weight gain (Fig. 8) due to slow volumetric moisture ingress.

Fig. 6. The weight gain of dried nanocomposite and neat epoxy after being exposed to 95% relative humidity for both 0.1 mm and 1 mm thick films.

Fig. 7. Electrical conductivity changes of 0.1 mm and 1 mm thick samples over time.

Fig. 8. Electrical conductivity changes of 0.1 mm and 1 mm thick samples versus weight gain when humidity increasing from 10% to 95% RH.

Fig. 9 shows the electrical conductivity change of thin nanocomposite films over time under cyclic humidity change (between 10% RH and 95% RH). The first cycle results in a large reduction of conductivity (about 40%). This is attributed to the fact that the humidity desorption is slower than the humidity absorption. For the second cycle and afterwards, further conductivity drops of a smaller magnitude ($\sim 4\%$ per each humidity cycle) were recorded. Several researchers have suggested that the swelling of polymer layer between CNT-CNT junctions in nanocomposites due to humidity (i.e., increasing tunneling barriers) is the reason for an increase in the electrical resistance [9-10]. A permanent reduction of $\sim 4\%$ per each humidity cycle is attributed to permanent damage in the electrical conductivity network due to repetitive swelling and shrinkage of polymer layers located between CNT-CNT junctions.

Fig. 9. Electrical conductivity changes of 0.1 mm nanocomposite film over time under repetitive humidity change.

4. Conclusion

The effect of temperature, mechanical strain and humidity on the electrical conductivity of a CNT-modified epoxy material was examined. For the range of examined temperature (25-100°C), the nanocomposite electrical conductivity was insensitive to temperature change. On the other hand, it was observed that humidity significantly influenced the conductivity of the nanocomposite due to moisture ingress. This influence largely depends of the geometry (the thickness in this case) of the nanocomposite. Upon the maturation of technology for the utilization of CNT for electrical and sensing applications, it will be necessary to

understand the influence of environmental factors such as humidity on targeted applications. The nanocomposite developed in this study demonstrated sensitivity to mechanical strain with a gauge factor of 3.7. This means a 3.7% change in resistivity (or conductivity) when a strain of 1% is applied to the sensor. In comparison, a maximum water uptake can cause 80% reduction in conductivity. This suggests that for most practical applications when strain is below 1%, the nanocomposite is more sensitive to small humidity changes (e.g., 5%) than the strain itself. This means that the effect of humidity should be compensated. Similarly, if electrical conductivity networks of CNT are used for damage detection, it is important to consider the role humidity can play in interpreting the damage size. A permanent increase in resistance due to cyclic humidity change can also limit the application of CNTs for the development of conductive polymers and nano-based sensors.

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